

Discussion of the introduction of a new complex physical quantity

(bq, m_0) into physics

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Abstract: Here we present a new physical quantity with the aim of unifying the structure of physics. The basic assumption starts with a reduction of all natural forces into a single force. As a first step, we combine Coulomb's law and the law of gravity into a single law. Astonishingly, this new law introduces a force never before described, which takes the form of a mass-charge force. This new force may be responsible for holding together the atomic nucleus, counteracting the Coulomb repulsive force. As such, this nuclear force could also be integrated into the new force law. A reduction of the natural forces into a single force would also reduce the number of conservation laws. The discussion herein focuses only on whether gravitational and inertial masses are identical or have different properties: if velocity increases, inertial mass also increases, but gravitational mass appears to remain constant. Furthermore, this may make it possible to measure absolute γ - factors which are given by the quotient of the inertial and gravitational masses. If true, this would invalidate one of the postulates of the theory of special relativity, leaving the theory of relativity open to new interpretation. Introduction of the new quantity, the complex number consisting of charge and mass (bq, m_0) , would not, however, invalidate other well-known formulas of physics, for the following reasons: with respect to all equations relating to gravitational mass, the charges usually sum to zero, yielding $q = 0$ and $(bq, m_0) \cong m$, leading to no inconsistencies; with respect to all equations relating to charge, the error would similarly be negligible, since charge changes through m only by adding the summand m/b . Since the gravitational mass of an electron is very small, precise measurements are needed to verify this proposed complex relationship. The inertial mass, would remain as has been established.

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Résumé : Nous présentons ici une nouvelle quantité physique dans le but de simplifier la structure de la physique. L'hypothèse basique commence par une réduction de toutes les forces naturelles en une force unique. Comme premier pas, on combine la loi de Coulomb et la loi de gravitation de Newton en une seule loi physique. Ce qui est étonnant, c'est que la nouvelle loi, qui en résulte, introduit une nouvelle force, qui n'a pas encore été décrite et qui a la forme d'une force de charge- masse. Cette nouvelle force pourrait être responsable du fait, que les noyaux de l'atome restent ensemble quand elle s'oppose à la force de Coulomb. De cette façon, l'énergie nucléaire pourrait aussi s'intégrer dans la formule d'une nouvelle énergie physique. Une réduction de toutes les forces naturelles en une seule force pourrait donc réduire le nombre de lois de conservation. En plus, il en résulte la question de savoir si la masse de gravitation et l'inertie ont des propriétés identiques ou différentes. Si la vitesse augmente, l'inertie augmente également; la masse gravitationnelle reste cependant constante. Il en résulte alors la possibilité que les facteurs gamma (γ) absolus pourraient se produire par la formation du quotient de l'inertie et de la masse gravitationnelle. Si il en était ainsi, un des postulats de la théorie de la relativité serait faux et la théorie de la relativité devrait être réinterprétée. L'introduction de cette nouvelle quantité, le nombre complexe se composant d'une charge et d'une masse (bq, m_0), ne contredirait cependant pas les lois physiques existantes bien connues. Et ceci pour la raison suivante: en tenant compte de toutes les équations concernant la masse gravitationnelle, les charges positives et négatives de même grandeur s'additionnent et finissent par faire zéro $q = 0 \Rightarrow (bq, m_0) \cong m$ de sorte qu'il n'en résulte aucune inconsistance. En tenant compte de toutes les équations concernant la charge, l'erreur serait également négligeable étant donné que les charges changeraient seulement par l'addition du terme de la somme m/b et que b est très grand. Comme la masse gravitationnelle d'un électron ne peut être que très petite, des mesures très précises sont nécessaires pour

prouver expérimentalement cette relation complexe ici postulée. L'inertie resterait une quantité physique bien établie.

Keywords:

Gravitational Law; Coulomb Law; Lorentz Transformation; Galilean Transformation;
Unification; Charge; Mass; Inertia; Relativity; Absolute Space

I. INTRODUCTION

A. Structure of Physics

Unification of the structure of physics has long been an important goal for physicists. Here, a new attempt at such unification is presented. Although, at first sight, there may appear to be discrepancies between the assumptions made and experimental results, these differences do not necessarily conflict with the ideas presented, as they may likely be attributed to measurement errors or additional effects for which the experimental interpretations have not accounted. The primary reason for introducing the quantity (bq, m_0) is that it makes possible formalization of the various sub-fields of mechanics and electrostatics into a single, uniform theory. Until now, attempts at producing a unified theory have considered only certain pairs of forces: the electrostatic and magnetic force, the electromagnetic and the weak force, or the electroweak and the strong force. However, none of these combinations take into account the gravitational force. Therefore, while in principle we believe this new theory to be consistent with existing theories, unconventional approaches must be adopted to include consideration of the gravitational force. The hypotheses that $z = bq + mi = (bq, m_0)$ is the basic idea presented here and all conclusions arise from this assumption.

B. Motivation for the Introduction of (bq, m_0)

Previous attempts to unify the various sub-fields of physics with a single theory have failed to include gravitation. As will be shown, our new quantity (bq, m_0) , where b : constant; q : charge; m_0 : gravitational mass, allows for the development of a unified theory that includes gravity, while also maintaining the validity of all well-known formulas of physics. Thereby (bq, m_0) is thought to be a new defined kind of charge, able to replace the well known electrical charge q and the gravitational charge m_0 . The advantage of this theory is that it raises no inconsistencies with currently accept physical principles that govern the planet. With regard to equations concerning mass, because charge quantities usually sum to zero,

$$q = 0 \Rightarrow (bq, m_0) \cong m \quad (1)$$

With regard to equations concerning charge, the error is negligible since the value for the charge increases only by adding the summand m/b :

$$(q \cong q' + m_0 / b) \quad (2)$$

Furthermore, because the mass of the electron is small and the constant b has a high value, very precise measurements are needed to experimentally validate the proposed complex quantity. The integration of quantum theory into the concepts presented here may also be viable.

C. Unified Force Law

The mathematical equivalence of the law of gravity and Coulomb's law is striking. This equivalence suggests that they may describe the same physical law. Combining mass and charge into a complex quantity:

$$z = (bq, m_0) = bq + mi \quad (3)$$

where b is set to be 11×10^9 kg/C and leading for the force to:

$$F^c = G \frac{z_1 \cdot z_2}{r^2} \quad (4)$$

with F^c : complex force, G : gravitational constant, z_1 and z_2 are (q_1, m_{o1}) and (q_2, m_{o2}) of two bodies 1 and 2 and r is the distance between these bodies 1 and 2. This yields a single force law that describes both gravitational and electrostatic interactions. Letting the charge of a body go to zero and considering only gravity leaves the law of gravity preserved in its original form. On the other hand, if the body being observed has a nonzero charge, then the combined law yields Coulomb's law.

This formulation combines gravitational mass and charge into a single quantity, and the result is a single law describing both gravitational and electrostatic interactions. If the charge of a body is zero and only gravity is being considered, then the combined law yields the Law of Gravity. However, if the body being observed has a nonzero charge, then the combined law yields Coulomb's Law. Constants are selected in a way that kg^2 , C^2 and $\text{kg} \times \text{C}$ all result in N (Newton).

Thereby this law defines a new, complex force. Expanding this new force law yields:

$$F^c = G \frac{z_1 \cdot z_2}{r^2} = F_{q_1 q_2} + F_{q_1 m_2} i + F_{q_2 m_1} i + 2F_{m_1 m_2} i^2 \underset{q, m_1 = q, m_2}{=} F_{qq} + 2F_{qm} i + 2F_{mm} i^2 \quad (5a)$$

$$= F_{qq} - F_{mm} + 2F_{qm} i = (F_{qq} - F_{mm}; 2F_{qm}) = (F_C - F_N; 2F_{qm}) \quad (5b)$$

with $F_{qq} = F_C$: charge charge force, Coulombs force; F_{qm} : charge mass force; $F_{mm} = F_N$: mass mass force, Newton's force. Within these equations novel imaginary forces appear. Therefore for the interpretation of imaginary forces an operational framework is needed. Here the following operational framework is proposed: imaginary forces are regarded to be attractive and to be as real as all other well known forces (F):

$$F = \sum_i F_i = F_C - F_N + 2iF_{qm} \quad (6a)$$

$$F = \sum_i F_i = F_C - F_N - 2F_{qm} \quad (6b)$$

Of cause this assumption has to be confirmed experimentally. In addition to the Law of Gravity and Coulomb's Law, the unified law of force derived here contains an additional, new force: the mass-charge binding force. This new force has not yet been observed experimentally, and it has not yet been used to explain any phenomena. In the following it is assumed that this new mass charge force is as real as all other forces and that it works in an attracting direction comparable to the Newtonian gravitation force and thus that it is negative.

Also other authors have already thought of and described an mass charge force e.g. Lo^{1,2}. But while Lo and others thought of the mass charge force as of a repulsive force¹, the mass charge force as described here is considered to be an attractive force comparable to the gravitational force. An attractive force working between charge and mass already is described in every physics textbook and named “electrostatic induction” (in German textbooks this force is named “influence”). This force commonly is explained by an induced charge separation in the mass through the influence of the electric field surrounding the charge approaching the mass. Of course –no doubt about this– this effect exists, however it might be possible and is predicted here that this effect overlays another smaller effect that has therefore not been detected up until now. This smaller and potentially overlaid phenomenon is the interaction of mass and charge. It is obvious that if both effects exist, both act together overlaying each other.

Already in 1572 Rafael Bombelli³ thought of imaginary numbers as of numbers with a special kind of a negative algebraic pre-sign. From a pure mathematical point of view the difference between the negative numbers (-1) and (i) results in its origin from the definition, that $(-1) \times (-1) = (+1)$. At this point an asymmetry between the (-1) - negative to the well known positive numbers arises, since a positive number always keeps positive even if multiplied with another positive number. On the other hand a negative number times a negative number result in a positive number. However there is only limited evidence for this definition and $(i) \times (i) = (-1)$ is an acceptable alternative to this mathematical definition: A negative number that keeps being negative, if multiplied with another negative number.

Because of the physical context here and because of the mathematical analogy explained as a mathematical formalism the number “ i ” is regarded to be able to be dropped-out of the equations here, but only at the end of a calculation as last step of this particular calculation. If it would be dropped-out before, of cause a wrong result might be obtained. The dropping-out of “ i ” from an equation then is equally to the statement, that the mass- charge interaction is regarded being as real as the mass-mass interaction (gravity) and as the charge-charge interaction (electrostatic interaction).

The atomic nucleus contains positively charged nucleons (protons) and neutral nucleons (neutrons), both of which have gravitational mass. The force proposed here to exist between gravitational mass and charge may hold the nucleons together.

In the formulas above (5, 5a, 5b, 6), complex forces arise. So far all physical quantities are described, at least in classical physics, mathematically exclusively using real numbers (R).

However in electrical engineering and in quantum physics complex numbers already arise. Also in these sub-disciplines so far is assumed that the complex numbers needed are a pure mathematical method without any actual physical relevance for reality. Complex numbers are thought to be purely mathematical tools. However here in the present paper a different train of thought is persuaded: It can also be that some physical quantities actually are complex quantities and are mathematically better described using complex quantities.

However since we are limited in our experience of the everyday life on the real part of the physical quantities, it might be that imaginary components are hidden to us. However this does not mean that these imaginary components do not exist. The existence of imaginary force-components and their physical relevance have to be clarified by physical experiments.

The design and conduction of experiments in order to proof the questionably effect of imaginary force- components is strongly suggested hereby. Very sensitive measuring equipment is necessary for the proof, since imaginary components appear in parallel with real components, whereby the real components are much larger in most cases.

Following the thesis of the present paper imaginary forces are just as material as real forces. For the working- direction it is assumed that imaginary forces act into same direction as forces with a negative sign (minus), since the quantity i just like the quantity $-i$ are both very similar to the number -1 . It is well possible that it concerns with the so called dark matter and with the so called dark energy to effects of the imaginary components of well-known physical quantities. Further more some new experiments conducted at the CERN lead to new questions concerning the correctness of the theory of relativity. Thereby it has to be added that an absolute interpretation of movement is better in agreement with the interpretation of complex forces as presented here compared to a relative interpretation.

D. Mass-Charge Force

In addition to the law of gravity and Coulomb's law, the unified law of force derived here contains an additional new force: the mass-charge binding force. As of yet, this new force has neither been observed experimentally, nor has it been used to explain any phenomena.

The atomic nucleus contains positively charged nucleons (protons) and neutral nucleons (neutrons), both of which have mass. The force proposed here between mass and charge may be responsible for holding the nucleons together, where this possibility will be considered more closely in conclusion III. A correlation between the difference of the attractive mass-

charge product and the repulsive Coulomb potential, on one hand, and the nuclear binding energy, on the other, is established with high statistical significance and high statistical power ($N = 3000$ nuclides investigated). Analysis of the square correlation coefficients k_0 , k_1 and k_2 of all the different isobars, obtained by square correlating the nuclear binding energies (E) of the isobars to the nuclide charge numbers

$$E = const_2 \cdot Z^2 + i \cdot const_1 \cdot ZA + const_0 \quad (7a)$$

$$E = k_2 Z^2 + k_1 Z + k_0 \quad (7b)$$

reveals that their quotients k_1/k_2 depend absolutely linearly on nuclear masses (linear correlation coefficient $r^2 = 0.998$, Pearson's $r = 0.999$). This means that the linear charge-dependent term of the nuclear binding energy also depends linearly on mass.

E. Conservation Laws

Reduction of the natural forces has astonishing consequences for the conservation laws: several conservation equations can be combined in a single conservation law using the complex quantity $z = (bq, m_0)$. The resulting law contains the charge conservation law as well as the conservation equations of several mass associated quantities, such as baryon number, lepton number and rest energy. In this unified conservation law, antimatter is assumed to possess negative mass ($-i \cdot m_0$) and positive energy:

$$\sum_j z_j = b \sum_j q_j + i \sum_j m_{oj} = const \quad (8)$$

This equation is true for the “charge” aspect of a given mass. If you split “mass” into the gravitational-mass according to Newton’s law of gravitation and into inertia according to Newton’s law of acceleration then this reduction of the conservation laws applies to the gravitational- mass first, since this mass aspect is absolute analogue or almost “complex-identical” as assumed here to the electrical charge. However this does not apply to inertia in the same strict way, since inertia as a form of energy can be converted into other forms of energy as we all now.

F. To the Theory of Relativity

An important tenet of the theory of relativity is that the inertial mass of a body increases with its velocity. A simultaneous increase of (bq, m_0) ; so of charge and gravitational mass would probably not make sense because such a relationship would not be physically meaningful. Therefore, inertial mass and gravitational mass may not be identical; rather, they are distinct properties. The ratio of the inertial mass to the gravitational mass could be equal to the γ -factor. If this is so, then this quotient could be used to precisely define absolute velocity at each point in time for any object.

This reasoning has consequences for current interpretations of the theory of relativity: it gives rise to the possibility that velocity no longer be regarded as a purely relative phenomenon but as one that can be defined absolutely. If true, this would invalidate one of the postulates of the theory of relativity. Nevertheless, the formulas of theory of relativity would remain valid, although their interpretation must be altered. In conclusion II an attempt is made to interpret the special theory of relativity using the premises described above. Conclusion II also shows that, with some modifications, the special theory of relativity is consistent with the theory described here. As will be discussed, motion can be clearly distinguished from non-motion because of length contraction, time dilation, and mass increase. Maintaining the validity of the basic tenets of theory of relativity means simultaneously accepting a splitting of reality (e.g. the twin paradox), or accepting a theory with an underlying inconsistency.

G. To Relativism and Absolutism

It is important to consider that, given the correctness of the theory described here, it is impossible to have an inertial system at absolute rest, $a = 0$. As known from the inertial

system moving at the speed of light c , an inertial system at rest with $\gamma = 1$ would also be similarly unattainable. From the exclusive view of the theory of relativity, the spectrum of possible motions and inertial systems quasi-recursively repeatedly begins anew. The initial considerations assumed here lead to elimination of this recursion, making the physical universe substantially smaller and clearer.

H. To the Rydberg Constant

In Conclusion I, we discuss that introduction of the new physical quantity (bq, m_0) implies a corresponding increase in the Rydberg constant by the γ factor of motion. This velocity dependence could possibly explain the behavior of galaxies far away without postulating the existence of dark matter, and it should be experimentally verifiable. Conclusion I also describes a possible connection between the unified theory presented here and the theory of quantum mechanics.

I. Gravitation and Inertia

Modern physics uses one word to describe two different things: mass describes both gravitation and inertia. Although these quantities are proportional to each other on earth, they may not be the same under all conditions. Gravitation describes a mass-mass interaction according to Newton's gravitational law, while inertia describes a resistance against acceleration according to Newton's law of motion ($F = ma$). Thus, the theory presented here attempts to separate gravitation and inertia. It combines gravitational mass and charge into a complex quantity (bq, m_0) . Inertia remains the well-known scalar quantity m from the existing Newtonian theory.

As stated by the theory of relativity, inertia increases with velocity. The quantity (bq, m_0) gravitational mass and charge, in contrast, don't seem to increase with velocity, particularly since charge does not also increase. This is described by

$$m = m_0\gamma \quad (9)$$

(m : inertia, m_0 : gravitational mass), and we postulate that this relationship should replace the equivalence principle. Since the value of γ on earth is nearly 1, the equivalence principle remains valid on earth. Interestingly, this suggests that charge can form from nonentity as positive and negative entities (e.g., through β -decay) under energetically favorable conditions. Mass objects however, cannot be formed from nonentity since gravitational mass is associated with inertia ($m = m_0\gamma$), and inertia requires energy for its formation. Since there is no such thing as negative energy

$$E = |m| \cdot c^2 \quad (10)$$

a difference between charge and inertial mass must, therefore, remain. Thereby energy and inertial mass are not conserved quantities, since they can be converted into each other; however their sum should also be a conserved quantity

$$\sum_j E_j + c^2 \cdot \sum_j m_j = \text{const.} \quad (11)$$

with E: Energy, m: inertial mass and c: speed of light.

J. Proposal of two Experiments to verify the new Theory:

The theory we describe is a likely candidate for the grand unified theory of theoretical physics (GUT) or the theory of everything (TOE). Two major conclusions flow from it, and both should be verifiable experimentally.

Experiment 1

1.) Einstein's special theory of relativity has already established that the inertial mass of an object should increase with a corresponding increase in the γ factor related to the object's velocity. However, in contrast to Einstein's theory, the theory described here should apply not only to simple relative motions but also to complex motions. It should also apply to compound complex motions, such as that of an electron orbiting a moving nucleus. It therefore follows that the masses of the electrons orbiting around a nucleus also increase by the γ factor of their velocity. Since the Rydberg constant depends on the mass of the orbiting

electrons, the value of the Rydberg constant of the atom concerned should also increase by the γ factor of the orbiting electrons.

The velocity of the orbiting electrons results in either moving atoms or moving ions, according to the relativistic addition of velocities from the velocity of the atoms and from the path velocity of the electrons. This effect should shift the spectral lines of highly accelerated ions toward higher frequencies (blue shift). In addition to the shift predicted here, both Doppler effects, the relativistic Doppler effect (2nd order) and the frequency shift due to motion of the transmitter and receiver (1st order), must be taken into account.

The experiment proposed here uses spectroscopy (i.e., absorption or emission of light) to ask the following question regarding rapidly accelerated ions: “How do the whole spectra of rapidly moving ions compare with those of ions at rest, and what is the best explanation for differences between these spectra?” While the relativistic Doppler Effect leads to a reduction in the resonance frequency (red shift), the predicted dependence of the Rydberg constant on γ leads to an increase in the resonance frequency (blue shift). In order for electrons to maintain their orbit around the atomic nucleus with an increasing mass and increasing centrifugal force, it must be assumed that the path velocity of the orbiting electrons ($\sim 2\%$ of c) slows as the atom accelerates. As a result of this effect, the atom can buffer the velocity of an electron over a wide range. Therefore, a blue shift is assumed to arise only when the atom or ion is moving at high velocity ($v \rightarrow c$). In contrast, a red shift smaller than the value given by the relativistic Doppler effect may be observable. Thereby the proposed experiment is similar to the one done by Ives and Stilwell in 1938⁴, but it should be made at clearly higher velocities of the accelerated ions and it should include the whole spectra and not just only single lines as e.g. the one done by Reinhardt, Saathoff, Buhr, Carlson, Wolf, Schwalm, Karpuk, Novotny,

Huber, Zimmermann, Holzwarth, Udem, Hänsch and Gwinner in 2007⁵. There are already experiments reported that did not confirm the transversal Doppler effect as predicted by the special theory of relativity of Albert Einstein as the one done by Thim in 2003⁶.

Experiment 2

2.) From the considerations above, it follows that there should be a fundamental interaction between mass and charge. The magnitude of such interaction must be in-between that of the charge-charge interaction (Coulomb) and of the well-known mass-mass interaction (gravitation). This interaction should lead to a slight spatial anisotropy in the motion of a charged particle on the earth's surface. Two experiments may be useful for verifying the existence of this fundamental interaction:

2a) First, one could accelerate charged particles, such as an electron together with a photon, along the same course. Due to the large mass of the earth, the flight path of the charged particle (electron) should diverge from that of the photon. This diversion should be several orders of magnitude greater than that caused by gravitation.

2b) Second, one could verify the spatial anisotropy of motion as follows. The flight path of a charged particle should change if the accelerating equipment is rotated around the longitudinal axis of motion by 180° . If the accelerating equipment were calibrated such that the charged particle accelerated along a precisely straight path, such as parallel with a photon, then the flight path should change when the accelerating equipment is rotated by 180° . In this case, the equipment compensating for the diversion of the charged particle would rotate, so compensation would no longer be given.

In contrast with Experiment 1, the charged particles in Experiment 2 do not need to be highly accelerated. The use of a smaller velocity in Experiment 2, however, would result in even more precise detections and measurements.

II. THEORY

A.1. As a First Conclusion (I), it follows that the new physical Quantity (bq, m_0) leads to an increase in Rydbergs Constant by the γ factor of Motion.

According to the special theory of relativity, motion is always relative. The concept of absolute space therefore makes no sense in the framework of this theory. However, as suggested in this paper, invalidation of the relative nature of motion does not necessarily negate the remaining conclusions and formulas of the theory of relativity. If motion were absolute and not relative, and if there were such a thing as absolute space, we probably could have already reached a considerable γ factor in the reference system of our earth. Relative velocity remains independent of the reference system, which means that it is invariant. “Relativistic effects”, in absolute terms, may then be observable at considerably lower velocities. Several cosmological questions depend on the interpretation of spectral shifts. The following discussion addresses these cosmological questions by assuming velocity dependence of the Rydberg constant.

2. γ –Dependence of Rydbergs Constant

According to Bohr’s atomic model, the Rydberg constant depends on the mass of the electron, or more correctly, on its inertia. The mass of the electron is generally considered to be constant. If a relativistic mass increase is taken into account, the Rydberg constant depends on the γ – factor of the electron under observation. This relationship becomes particularly

important when it is assumed, as described above, that the relativistic mass increase is relevant at lower velocities, or stated more correctly, at lower relative velocities. In addition to the Rydberg constant, the spectral frequencies of atoms depend on the γ factor, which results in a blue shift

$$R' = R \cdot \gamma \quad (12)$$

due to the γ -dependence of inertia

$$m = m_0 \gamma \quad (9)$$

3. Spectral Shift of Distant Galaxies

Based on the conclusions above, the interpretation of spectra of distant galaxies should consider not only the Doppler red shift ($f' = k \cdot f$), but also the blue shift caused by the velocity dependence of the Rydberg constant ($R' = R \cdot \gamma$). Taken together, these two effects lead to the following expression for the frequency shift:

$$f' = k \cdot \gamma \cdot f \quad (13)$$

4. Changes in the Acceleration of the Expansion of the Universe

Recent astronomical investigations suggest that the rate of expansion of the universe is accelerating; in other words, the values of the red shifts of distant galaxies are increasing. To explain this phenomenon, the concepts of dark energy and accelerated expansion of the universe were previously introduced. However, another explanation for the increasing red shifts of distant galaxies could possibly be derived from the equation $f' = k \cdot \gamma \cdot f$ given above. If the absolute velocities of distant galaxies were already at a significant fraction of the speed of light, the observed red shift should be given by the product $k \cdot \gamma$. If the galaxy slows down and no longer accelerates, k will increase, while at the same time, the γ factor will decrease. However, the product $k \cdot \gamma$ will decrease if the galaxy's initial absolute velocity is a

significant fraction of the speed of light. In this case, the rotational velocity will decrease. It is also likely that Hubble's law must be modified accordingly, from

$$v = k_{Hubble} \cdot d \text{ to } v = k_{Hubble} \cdot d / \gamma \quad (14)$$

(v : velocity; k_{Hubble} : Hubbles constant; d : distance; γ : γ -factor).

5. Brightness of Supernovas Type 1

Another argument frequently cited to support the accelerated expansion of the universe is the constant brightness of all *type-1a supernovas* and the discrepancy between the distance of the exploding stars from earth and their brightness measured on earth. The brightness measured is generally weaker than would be expected for their distances. Insight into this discrepancy may be gained by studying supernova explosions, which provide a glimpse into the past because their red shift reveals their previous expansion. As described above, the conventional interpretation of this red shift does not take into account the γ dependency hypothesized here for the Rydberg constant or the resulting blue shift. If velocities were greater in the past than they are now, there should be a considerable blue shift due to the γ dependence of the Rydberg constant, which must be accounted to the measured red shift. This results in a larger Doppler-related red shift which, therefore, suggests a larger expansion velocity in the past. If the brightness measured at present for the supernova is less than predicted based on the distance from the earth, then it is because the measured red shift is too small. The brightness measurements suggest that the supernovas are farther away than their calculated distances. Taking into account the additional blue shift due to the Rydberg constant clearly shows that the red shift based on the Doppler Effect must be larger than what is currently measured, and that taking this into account to the red shift can yield agreement with the measured brightness.

6. Rotational Velocity of the Spiral Arms of Galaxies

The rotational velocity of outer stars in the spiral arms of galaxies are known to be too high to fit to a *Keplerian velocity distribution* of these stars. One explanation of this is that large halos of so-called dark matter are assumed to surround the galaxies. Until now, however, a possible γ factor of the earth has not been taken into account. In a *Keplerian velocity distribution*, the γ factor of the earth (or of inner stars) should be larger than the γ factors of stars moving farther out in a galaxy; therefore, the blue shift should also be larger than that of the outer stars, due to the dependency of the Rydberg constant on γ . Thus, the outer stars show a smaller blue shift and a correspondingly larger red shift in their spectral lines. This additional blue shift must be accounted to the measured red shift to retain the red shift due to the Doppler Effect. This plausible explanation of the observed red shift can probably renders the assumption of halos of dark matter unnecessary.

7. Origin of Structures in the Universe

A further puzzle in modern astrophysics is the formation of galaxies and stars from the homogeneous and isotropic plasma released by the Big Bang. This can be resolved by assuming a mass-charge force and a mass-charge binding energy, without having to invoke dark matter. In contrast to gravity, the mass-charge binding energy is neither homogeneous nor isotropic; it exists only between mass-rich neutrons and charge-rich particles such as protons. In contrast with electrons, no interactions occur between protons and photons that destroy the resulting structures. The assumption of a mass-charge force could possibly provide an explanation for both structure formation and "Silk"-damping, obviating the need to invoke the existence of dark matter.

8. Relativistic Length Contraction and Connections between the New Theory and the Theory of Quantum Mechanics

According to the special theory of relativity, length contracts in the direction of motion in a moving inertial system with increasing velocity. In an inertial system at rest, however, the same moving body seems to cover the same complete distance as at rest. The question now arises: “How does a moving inertial system fit into an inertial system at rest?”

In principal, the moving inertial system can adapt itself to the stationary inertial system in either a fine or coarse manner. For each case, there are points in the stationary inertial system that are **not present** in the moving inertial system, and the moving body is, therefore, **non-existent** in the stationary inertial system at these point. If a moving system is observed to start from a stationary inertial system, then the moving body sequentially exhibits points of existence and non-existence resulting in a sequence of differing residence probabilities. This sequence can occur at high or low frequencies. Therefore, every moving body can possibly be described as a wave of existence and non-existence. This *existence/non-existence wave* could be equal to *Schroedinger's wave function*, and could, moreover, follow from Lorentz's length contraction (l : length, l_0 : length at rest, γ : γ -factor):

$$l/l_0 = 1/\gamma \tag{15}$$

Interestingly, it is possible to show that the integrals

$$\int \gamma dt/t_0 = \sqrt{1 - \frac{v^2}{c^2}} \tag{16a}$$

$$\int \gamma dx = ct \cdot \sin^{-1}\left(\frac{x}{ct}\right) \tag{16b}$$

describe sinus functions equal to the dimensionless Schroedinger's wave function ϕ . Please note that the calculations shown here describe more of an analogy between Schroedinger's equation and the integral of the γ function than a strictly mathematical derivation.

By these calculations, γ is not seen as a constant but rather as a function of x and t that describes the structure of space and time.

In short:

$$\int \varphi dx / x_0 = \iint \gamma dx dt / (x_0 t_0), \text{ with } dx_0 = \gamma \cdot dx \Rightarrow \int \varphi^2 dx / x_0 = \sqrt{1 - \frac{x^2}{c^2 t^2}} \quad (17)$$

This leads to the basic question: “Is it possible to combine the *probability wave* derived from theory of relativity with *Schroedinger’s equation*?” A hint that the answer may be “yes” comes from considering that the probability of hitting a point of the moving body in a stationary system is given by the quotient $l/l_0 = 1/\gamma$. This results in an existence probability

$$p \equiv \sqrt{(1 - v^2 / c^2)} \quad (18)$$

(p : probability to meet the object in the distance from 0 to x at a given time t).

For *Schroedinger’s function*, this becomes

$$\varphi^2 = p = \sqrt{(1 - v^2 / c^2)} \quad (19)$$

Thus, it is interesting that, for this function, *Schroedinger’s equation* holds true: $\varphi_t = \varphi_{xx} + \varphi - 1$. According to the *de Broglie equation*, the frequency of the probability wave is clearly determined by the kinetic energy and thus by the inertia. Therefore, it seems that bodies with high inertia move through a “finer network” of *existence and non-existence* than bodies with lower inertia. Objects with a greater inertial mass are more connected to and with space; expressed in German, these objects show a higher “Verwebtheit”, “interweaving” with space according to $E = h \cdot \nu$ (E : energy; h : Plancks constant; ν : frequency). Thus, it is not only at higher velocities that relativistic effects are likely to appear: with the assumption of an *absolute space*, relativistic effects should become relevant at considerably lower velocities ($v \ll c$).

9. To the Planck Units

Planck units follow from the assumption that the minimum energy is given by $m_{Planck} \cdot c^2$.

The corresponding *Planck time* is given by $h/(m_{Planck} \cdot c^2)$, and the *Planck length* is the length traversed by light in the smallest amount of time, i.e., the *Planck time*.

B.1. As a Second Conclusion (II), Absolute Motion follows from the Introduction of the new physical Quantity (bq, m_0) , according to the Rules of Theory of Relativity.

By introducing the physical quantity (bq, m_0) , gravitational mass and charge can be united. In order for this to work, gravitational mass and inertia must be treated as separate properties since inertia is a function of velocity whereas gravitational mass is not. Therefore, in distant highly accelerated galaxies, the proportionality factor of gravitational mass and inertia can be different from ours, and the question arises whether inertia is relative or absolute together with motion. Changing the frame of reference changes the mathematical description of physical processes, and classical mechanics assumes that the *Galilean transformation* is a suitable description for such a change in the frame of reference. The analogue in the field of electromagnetism is the *Lorentzian transformation*.

It occurred to Albert Einstein to not only use the *Lorentzian transformation* to describe the physics of electromagnetism but to extend its use so that it would remain valid even if the frame of reference changes. As a result, length, time, and inertial masses could no longer be regarded as constants independent of the frame of reference; instead, they were regarded as a function of velocity. The *Galilean transformation* is equivalent to the relativity principle in that every inertial system is equally valid for the description of physical processes. The following discussion focuses on the extent to which the *Lorentzian transformation* remains compatible with the relativity principle. It is possible that the *Lorentzian transformation*

describes a coordinate transformation in an absolute space in which the relativity principle is invalid. The purpose of the following discussion is not to logically deny the relativity principle but, rather, to ask the question, “Does renouncing it in its general form lead to a better description of reality?” Nevertheless, the constancy of the speed of light and the *Lorentzian transformation* will be retained as experimentally confirmed results.

2. To the Relativity Principle

The relativity principle states that, in all inertial systems, all physical laws are valid in the same form; however, the external form of the relativity laws is not explored here. Nevertheless, the physical laws contain the parameters length, time, and inertial mass. The following discussion assumes that these parameters change from one inertial system to another. If this is correct, one can differentiate between invariant quantities (laws, charge) and variable quantities (inertial mass, time, length). As a result, the general formulation of the relativity principle is most likely no longer valid in its current form, as will be discussed below.

3. Galilean Transformation

The *Galilean transformation* describes the change of velocities with a changing of the inertial system in classical mechanics. It deals only with a translation of the coordinates of the system and does not alter the principal changes in the phenomena under study. Since this transformation deals only with pure translational substitutions, all possible inertial systems are equally valid for the descriptions. Thus, the relativity principle follows; in other words, no frame of reference is specialized for the description of kinetic phenomena.

4. Lorentzian Transformation

Compared to the *Galilean transformation*, the *Lorentzian transformation* is much more complicated. It involves not a pure translation but rather a change in the system parameters.

This raises the question of whether the *Lorentzian transformation* suffices the relativity principle. Using the *Lorentzian transformation* the parameters length, time, and inertial mass are dependent on velocity. Thus, whether these parameters are applied to a stationary or a moving frame of reference becomes important. This is especially evident when summing velocities. In the *Galilean transformation*, velocity is the algebraic sum of the motion of individual objects, but this is not so in the case of the *Lorentzian transformation*. In order to determine which γ factor results from the observation of motion, it is important to know the initial γ factor in the chosen frame of reference. The constancy of the speed of light (c) remains uninfluenced by the *Lorentzian transformation* and the addition theorem, which stipulates that the speed of light measured in any frame of reference, has the same value, c .

These considerations should not, however, lead to the erroneous conclusion that the relativity principle is valid in its general form. If one is allowed to choose a moving frame of reference as a starting point for describing the speed of light, the only reason this velocity can be assumed to be constant is because, in this moving frame of reference, length and time have changed. Thus, the physics of inertial systems must change so as to maintain the constancy of the speed of light, which suggests that the relativity principle in its general form is no longer valid. This is particularly clear in the case of the addition theorem: each increase in velocity is accompanied by an increase in the γ factor. In a given inertial system, an observer can, therefore, determine that he is moving by measuring γ , but he cannot determine the direction in which he is moving without an external reference point.

Example given

Consider the following example. A body moves at 30% of the speed of light, and, in the frame of reference of this body, a second body also moves at 30% of the speed of light. With the usual description of the second body in the frame of reference of the first body, we calculate a γ factor of 1.048. If the motion of the first body, also moving at 30% of the speed of light ($\gamma = 1.048$), is also taken into account, the actual motion of the second body is calculated to be 55% of the speed of light. This velocity, however, corresponds to a γ factor of 1.197. For a system in which the first body moves at 99% of the speed of light and the second body also moves at 99% of the speed of light in the frame of reference of the first body, this effect is even clearer. Without taking the motion of the first body into account, a γ factor of 7 results for the second body; however, taking into account the motion of the first body yields a γ factor of 99 for the second body.

In this way, it is clear that the result depends on the choice of the frame of reference. In fact, it appears that a prerequisite for the *Lorentzian transformation* is a preferred, stationary absolute frame of reference. Naturally, one can take the view that both observers are correct and that the second body has both the γ factor 7 and the γ factor 99, depending on the frame of reference from which it is observed. As mentioned at the beginning, this paper is not intended to logically refute the relativity principle. Rather, this paper discusses the possibility that renouncing the principle may lead to a better description of reality. Keep in mind that it is the γ factor that determines the appearance of relativistic effects. The equation of motion for a body, according to $F = ma$, depends on its inertia, which, in turn, depends on the γ factor. Because of this, it is important to know whether we start with a γ factor of 7 or 99. It follows

that the *Galilean transformation* describes a transformation for a relative space, whereas the *Lorentzian transformation* describes a transformation in absolute space.

5. Possible Effects of an Absolute Space on the Physics of the Earth

Until now, the actual motion of our frame of reference, the earth, has not been taken into account. If one starts from the assumption that the earth itself moves, this may have consequences for the physical laws. Hence, it would be important to take into account the current γ factor of the earth.

Doing so would likely mean that, when the earth is the frame of reference, relativistic effects become important at much lower relative velocities than predicted by the theory of relativity and therefore need to be taken into account. Relativistic effects would thusly have to be included in the description of how the electron orbits the nucleus. Such an approach may also alter phenomena on a larger scale. Indeed, it is possible that relativistic effects already need to be considered to account for the behavior of distant galaxies.

6. Every γ factor corresponds to an Inertial System with “its own Physics”

If the relativity principle were no longer valid in its general form, every inertial system would have its own γ factor and thus “its own physics”. Analogously to the γ factor the k factor can be defined by $k_i = \sqrt{(1 + v_i / c) / (1 - v_i / c)}$. The transformation between inertial systems is given by the *Lorentzian transformation*. On earth, the velocity dependence of the γ factor would be described not by

$$\gamma = \frac{1}{\sqrt{1 - v^2 / c^2}} \quad (20)$$

but by

$$\gamma(v) = \frac{1}{2k_e} \cdot \sqrt{\frac{(c-v)}{(c+v)}} + \frac{1}{2k_e} \cdot \sqrt{\frac{(c+v)}{(c-v)}} \quad (21a)$$

or shorter

$$k_{total} = \prod_j k_j \quad (21b)$$

The latter equation results from the addition theorem. For $k_e = k_{earth} = 1$, the equation becomes simpler. Here k_e is defined by eq.(22a) and k_j by eq (22b):

$$k_e = \sqrt{(1+v/c)/(1-v/c)} \quad (22a)$$

$$k_j = \sqrt{(1+v_j/c)/(1-v_j/c)} \quad (22b)$$

is according to the Bondi k calculus, and for $k_e = k_{earth} = 1$ the equations become much simpler leading to the well known formulas. By measuring the velocity dependence of a γ -dependent quantity, it should be possible to determine k_{earth} from the above equation and thereby calculate the γ factor of the earth. With a single equation, one can determine the γ factor, and thus the physics, of all inertial systems.

7. Solution to the Paradoxes in the Theory of Relativity

The theory of relativity, as we know it, contains a series of paradoxes. The best known of these are the "twin paradox" and the "clock paradox." Because of the relativity principle, it is impossible to definitively state which twin has moved and which has not, or which has aged and which has not. The argument that both see each other only once during linear motion does not seem convincing since it admits the latent inconsistencies of reality. By excluding the principle of relativity in its general form and by choosing a fixed frame of reference, it becomes clear which twin moves and which does not. Thus, this paradox is resolved.

8. Dependence of the Rydberg Constant on Gamma

According to Bohr's model of the atom, the Rydberg constant depends on the mass of the electron, which is generally accepted as constant. If the relativistic mass increase of the electron is taken into account, it is possible to derive a dependence of the Rydberg constant on the γ factor for the electron being observed. This dependence is particularly important if, as described above, one starts from the assumption that the relativistic mass increase is already relevant, even at such "low velocities" as those found on earth.

9. The Spectral Shift of distant Galaxies

According to the descriptions above, interpretation of the spectra of distant galaxies must not only account for the Doppler red shift $f' = k \cdot f$ as before but also for a blue shift due to the relationship $R' = R \cdot \gamma$, which describes the dependence of the Rydberg constant on velocity. Thus, the frequency shift is given by $f' = k / \gamma \cdot f$. The resulting curve exactly reproduces the curves derived from studies of distant galaxies, which relate the frequency shifts to the distance between the galaxies' stars and their centers.

10. Line spectra of higher atom mass Elements

While the line spectrum of hydrogen can be satisfactorily described by Bohr's atomic model and the formulas derived from it, the Bohr model gives no exact data for clarifying the line spectra of elements larger than H or He. Since higher elements have higher nuclear charge numbers, the Coulomb force of attraction between the electron and nucleus is larger. Consequently, the velocity of the electrons in their orbits must also increase. This raises the question of whether relativistic effects are already present in modern observations. If they are, then taking into account the dependence of the Rydberg constant on γ should lead to unverified descriptions of the spectra of these elements.

Logically, the *Lorentzian transformation* seems to describe a transformation in absolute space, while the *Galilean transformation* seems to describe such a transformation in relative space.

It appears as if the relativity principle inherently assumes that space has a homogeneous structure. If space is not homogeneous, however, but rather changes with motion, then the relativity principle is no longer valid in its general form. This is because every inertial system can be described by its own γ factor such that its physics are valid. As a result, there should also be an inertial system with a γ factor of one ($\gamma = 1$) which is stationary, and relative to which absolute motions are defined. It is important to recognize that ignoring the strict relativity principle here only leads to an extremely small deviation for all known physical processes. These deviations are only relevant at high velocities in space or in atomic models. The measured constancy of the speed of light does not imply that the γ factor of the frame of reference in question is one, since the speed of light is the same in all reference frames.

11. Relativism and Absolutism

It is important to consider that, if the existence- probability difference between two reference systems is given by $p_1 \propto 1/\gamma_1$ and $p_2 \propto 1/\gamma_2$. Therefore, Einstein's theory of relativity maintains its existence-authorization and correctness. The difference in the theories lies, rather, within the fact that, by exclusively using the theory of relativity, the spectrum of possible motions and inertial systems recursively and repeatedly begins anew. However, using the theory suggested here, this recursivity would be eliminated. Thus, the universe would become substantially smaller and clearer.

12. Concerning the Invariance of Relative Velocity

The relative velocity of an object in a given frame of reference is defined by the distance traveled in a particular time. By taking into account length contraction and time dilation, one concludes that the distance traveled in a moving frame of reference is shortened by the factor $1/\gamma$. The time required to cover this distance in a moving frame of reference is also reduced by the factor $1/\gamma$. Thus, the relative velocity of the object is the quotient of the path difference and the time difference, γ cancels out, and so it is independent of the frame of reference used. Each observer obtains the same value for the relative velocity of the object. Only relative velocities and charges appear in the laws of electrodynamics, particularly in the Lorentzian force law, so these laws are largely independent of the frame of reference used and invariant. This fact likely prompted Einstein to formulate the general principle of relativity.

13. The Hafele-Keating Experiment and the Description of an Absolute Space

In 1971, Hafele and Keating flew around the earth, once westwards and once eastwards, accompanied by several atomic clocks. The result was that the observed time difference between the clocks depended on the path taken (westwards or eastwards). This experiment could be interpreted such that the principle of relativity would not apply to time. If relativity did apply to time, one would expect the same time difference for both directions. However, since time should depend on absolute motion and runs more slowly with increasing absolute velocity, a difference in times results depending on whether the direction traveled is with, or counter to, the spin of the earth. Further evidence of the fact that time depends on the absolute motion of an object comes from the need to correct the signals of GPS satellites, which is also analogous to Newton's bucket experiment.

14. Connection between Material Waves and the Theory of Relativity

The question arises as to whether quantum theory and the theory of relativity can be reconciled. One possibility for unifying the two theories lies in assuming the comprehensive isotropy of space. This idea originates in the possibility that the γ factor for a given body is a single quantity. In other words, there are not separate γ factors for every direction in space: only one γ factor describes all motion. As a result, numerous x-points of a coordinate system at rest would collapse seen from a moving coordinate system. In a stationary coordinate system, however, it would appear as if a moving particle can travel simultaneously between numerous spatially-separated points and interact with itself. Thus, it appears as a wave in the stationary coordinate system. The various possible paths in the stationary coordinate system, which collapse to one path in the moving system, appear as sums of probabilities, and these probabilities can interact with themselves.

One can also say that new points in space and time are generated when the coordinate system or frame of reference is changed to a slower coordinate system or frame of reference. The greater the difference in velocities between the initial and final systems or frames, the larger is the number of points that would be generated. The finer the structure, the smaller the observed wavelengths will be. The contraction in length during motion is a purely phenomenological description. The question arises as to why the length contraction and, in the reverse case, the length dilation occur. It seems that vacuum has simply been added in proportion to the difference in velocity: the greater the difference in velocity, the greater the vacuum added. In addition: the finer the points of existence distribution (concinnity) the higher the frequency the higher the associated energy according to

$$E = h \cdot \nu \tag{23}$$

Expressing the length contraction as a differential equation could possibly reveal a connection between quantum theoretical wave functions and the theory of relativity. In this equation, both variables appear: the lengths x and x_0 and the relative velocity (the time-dependent change of length, dx/dt). Integration of this differential equation

$$x = x_0 \cdot \gamma \quad (24)$$

leads to a wave

$$x = \sin(t) \quad (25)$$

function. By interpretation, this could mean that a moving frame of reference in a “stationary” frame of reference corresponds to a wave, and, accordingly, waves would not be material (or matter) properties but instead properties of space. However, this property of space is perceptible only on a microscopic scale.

This idea does not contradict to the conservation laws which must be true for all times, since points in time and space are generated parallel to each other and every real particle has a macroscopic (or microscopic) extension of at least several (mathematical) points. So only a part of the particle will disappear in space and then also in time.

C. As a Third Conclusion (III), the new physical Quantity (bq, m_0) implies the Existence of a new Force and Form of Energy.

The square of the complex quantity $(bq, m_0)^2$ contains the product of mass and charge, which shows a series of extraordinarily interesting correlations with other physical quantities. For all elements of the periodic system, there is a clear connection between the product of the atomic mass (A) and the nuclear charge number (Z), on the one hand, with the nuclear binding energy as given by the atomic mass defect, on the other. Consequently, there is a relationship between this product and the nuclear binding energy of each nuclide. This result can be interpreted as a force and a form of energy, which has never been described until now, which

hold together the atomic nucleus and overcomes the Coulomb repulsion due to the protons in the atomic nucleus. We call this new force and its associated energy the mass-charge force and the mass-charge binding energy. This force is proposed to replace the concepts of nuclear force and nuclear energy currently used in physics.

D. Observations of the Nuclear Binding Energy

If the nuclear binding energy per nucleon, or the equally important mass defect per nucleon, is plotted against the atomic number (mass or charge number) for all the elements of the periodic table, the well-known maximum curve of the nuclear binding energy is obtained. This graph shows a maximum at iron, which indicates the especially high stability of the iron nucleus. In principle, nuclei that are smaller than that of iron can be fused to form larger nuclei and release energy, while nuclei that are larger than that of iron can be split into smaller nuclei and also release energy.

One attempt to mathematically describe nuclear energy is the ‘mass formula’ proposed by Bethe and Weizsäcker:

$$E(Z, A) = a_v A - a_s A^{2/3} - a_c Z^2/A^{1/3} - a_a (N - Z)^2/(4A) - a_p \quad (26)$$

(E: Energy; A: mass number; Z: charge number; a_i : constant)

The Coulomb interaction is described here by the term $a_c Z^2/A^{1/3}$. This term is proportional to the square of the nuclear charge and inversely proportional to the radius of the nucleus, which itself grows as the cube root of the nucleon number. This model only gives an approximation of the nuclear binding energy. In addition, the formula contains some terms, such as the asymmetry and the pair terms, whose physical meanings are still unclear.

Other models used to describe the nucleus include the gas model and the shell model suggested by Fermi. The present paper is based on the observation that the product of the nuclear mass (A) and the nuclear charge number (Z) of each nuclide could also serve as a description of the nuclear binding energy. The theoretical nuclear mass of a nuclide is thereby given by the sum of the number of protons multiplied by the proton mass, together with the number of neutrons multiplied by the neutron mass. Furthermore, the new calculated quantity AZ is compared to well-known experimental quantities, i.e., the mass defects and the nuclear radii. The primary result of the data presented here is an **extremely significant correlation** ($r = 0.999$) between the k_1/k_2 quotient of the groups of isobars and their mass numbers. The k_1/k_2 quotient is thereby defined by the equation

$$E = const_2 \cdot Z^2 + i \cdot const_1 \cdot ZA + const_0 \quad (7a)$$

$$E = k_2 Z^2 + k_1 Z + k_0 \quad (7b)$$

where Z : charge number, E : nuclear binding energy, k_2 , k_1 and k_0 are correlation constants. According to the theory of the mass- charge interaction as introduced in the beginning (eq.5a, 5b, and 6) the term $k_1 Z$ should be related to the mass of the atom. Starting from this assumption the relationship between $k_1 Z$ and the mass number of the related atom A was investigated in more detail.

This lead to an astonishing linear correlation

$$E = const_2 Z^2 + 0.8 \cdot i \cdot const_2 ZA + const_0 \quad (27a)$$

$$E = k_2 Z^2 - 0.8 \cdot k_2 ZA + k_0 \quad (27b)$$

as will be shown here.

So, an extremely significant correlation of high statistical power ($N = 3000$ nuclides) between the nuclear binding energy, on the one hand, and the difference of the mass-charge product and the Coulomb potential, on the other, is presented here. This provides more support for the

introduction of the new quantity (bq, m_0) . Two kinds of groups were formed: groups of isobars ($A = \text{constant}$) and groups of isotopes ($Z = \text{constant}$), with all 3000 known nuclides filling each kind of the groups. Plotting the nuclear binding energy against the charge number reveals a square dependence for every group of isobars, which constituents have the same mass number but different charge numbers, and plotting the nuclear binding energy against the mass number for every group of isotopes similarly reveals a square dependence for each constituent (element). This result shows that there is an optimal amount of both charge and mass for an atomic nucleus. Analysis of the square correlation coefficients k_2 and k_1 of all the different possible groups of isobars shows a clear **linear dependence** of their quotient k_1/k_2 on the nuclear mass (linear correlation coefficient $r^2 = 0.998$, Pearson's $r = 0.999$). Analogously, the square correlation coefficient quotient l_1/l_2 of the groups of isotopes (different elements) shows a clear **linear dependence** on charge ($r^2 = 0.994$, Pearson's $r = 0.997$). These results can be explained by assuming a mass-charge force as described by the mass-charge product and counteracted by the Coulomb repulsion.

III. MATERIALS AND METHODS

A. Atomic masses

For the following calculations, the atomic masses of all 3000 known nuclides were used, as published by the KAERI (Korean Atomic Energy Research Institute). The use of such a large sample leads to a high statistical power. Most (that are, 2933) of these atomic masses are based on the results of G. Audi and A.H. Wapstra⁵. No other sources for atomic masses were used, and the atomic masses given were used for the correlations that follow. The 159 nuclear radii used for the comparison were taken from "Systematics of nuclear RMS charge radii" and "Numerical data and functional relationships in science and technology"^{8,9}.

Further more the software excel[®] (Microsoft[®], Redmont, WA, USA), a Intel[®] Celeron[®] Computer (Intel[®], Santa Clara, CA, USA) and a MacBookPro[®] (Apple[®], Cupertino, CA, USA) were used.

The nuclear binding energy of different isobaric elements plotted against the nuclear charge number Z leads to the known parabolic curves, which indicates that there is an optimal amount of charge that leads to the most stable nucleus. This square dependence reflects Coulomb's law. Similarly, the nuclear binding energy of different isotopes of an element plotted against the atomic mass number results in new parabolic curves, which have never before been reported. These curves show that for isobars, there is an optimal amount of charge, and for isotopes, there is an optimal amount of mass (new). Therefore, all known 3000 nuclides were grouped-in twice: into isobars and into isotopes.

B. Forming Groups of Isobars and Isotopes

For the well-known nuclides considered in this work, there were 269 groups of isobars (same mass number) formed and 110 groups of isotopes (same proton number). Thereby each group of isobars ($A=1,2,3,\dots$) comprised all nuclides with this specific mass number and each group of isotopes (elements, $Z=1,2,3,\dots$) comprised all nuclides (here isotopes) with this specific charge number, e.g. up to 25 nuclides (isotopes) in case of uranium. So every nuclide was grouped in multiple times here. The 110 isotope groups are identical to the 110 known elements and their constituent nuclides are the known isotopes of this specific element. Each individual group shows a square dependence of the binding energy as calculated from the mass defect (according to the atomic mass) with charge or mass number for isobars and isotopes, respectively. The calculated correlation coefficients for the square correlations were

calculated and listed for all isobar and isotope groups. Each group of isobars and/or isotopes yielded one set of square correlation coefficients.

Thereby (k_2, k_1, k_0) are defined as square correlation coefficients according to (7b):

$$E = const_2 \cdot Z^2 + i \cdot const_1 \cdot ZA + const_0 \quad (7a)$$

$$E = k_2 Z^2 + k_1 Z + k_0 \quad (7b)$$

for isobars of the same mass number A with E: binding energy, Z: charge number and k_i : constant. Analogously (l_2, l_1, l_0) are defined as the square correlation coefficients according to

$$E = const'_2 \cdot A^2 + i \cdot const'_1 \cdot ZA + const'_0 \quad (28a)$$

$$E = l_2 A^2 + l_1 A + l_0 \quad (28b)$$

for isotopes of the same charge number Z with E: binding energy, A: mass number and l_i : constant.

Correlation coefficients for the square correlations were calculated and are listed for all 269 groups of isobars leading to 269 (k_2, k_1, k_0) - triplets and for 110 groups of isotopes leading to 110 (l_2, l_1, l_0) -triplets.

The calculations were carried out in the following manner:

Step 1: Square correlations of the experimental nuclear binding energies (according to Audi and Wapstra) were calculated as a function of the atomic mass number A for all 110 groups of isotopes. Similarly, square correlations were carried out for the nuclear binding energies as a function of nuclear charge number Z for all 269 groups of isobars. Thus, the nuclear binding energy was correlated first versus the atomic mass number A for all isotopes of each element, and, analogously, the nuclear binding energy was correlated with the nuclear charge number Z for all isobaric nuclides for each group $(A=1,2,3,\dots)$. The resulting square correlation coefficients $l_2, l_1,$ and l_0 and $k_2, k_1,$ and k_0 are listed in the tables “isotopes” and “isobars”. The correlation coefficients were plotted as a function of mass number in the case of the isobars, or as a function of the charge number in the case of the isotopes.

Step 2: Linear correlation was carried out for all elements between the isotope coefficient ratio l_1/l_2 and the appropriate nuclear charge Z , and between the isobar coefficient ratio k_1/k_2 and the appropriate mass number A .

IV. RESULTS

A. Description of the Groups of Isotopes ($Z = \text{constant}$)

Evaluation of the groups of isotopes each constituting of nuclides with constant nuclear charge number Z reveals a quadratic relationship between the experimental binding energy (mass defect, atomic masses as given by the KAERI) and the mass number A . Formally, a quadratic relationship that describes the dependence of the binding energy on A can be written for the isotopes. This leads to an equation of the type

$$E = \text{const}'_2 \cdot A^2 + i \cdot \text{const}'_1 \cdot ZA + \text{const}'_0 \quad (28a)$$

$$E = l_2 A^2 + l_1 A + l_0 \quad (28b)$$

(where E : binding energy; l_i : coefficient; and A : mass number)

For all known nuclides, the correlation coefficients l_2 , l_1 , and l_0 were determined and were investigated for dependencies among themselves (see Figures. 1A-E). Especially for the first 50 elements of the periodic table, the correlation between the binding energy and the mass number A first seems to be a straight line and a parabolic curve for all others ($Z > 50$). Therefore, all elements are better described by the quadratic formula given above. The decrease in binding energy from $l_2 A^2$ with increasing mass number is either a radius effect or it due to an additional potential as postulated here: the mass-charge binding energy

$$l_1 A = ZA / r \quad (29)$$

B. Observation of the Ratios l_1/l_2 of the Groups of Isotopes and correlation with the Charge Number Z

The quotient l_1/l_2 shows a strict linear correlation ($r^2 = 0.994$, $r = 0.997$) with the charge number of the type $l_1/l_2 = -6Z$. This reflects the mass-charge binding energy (Figure 1A), leading to

$$E = const'_2 A^2 + 6 \cdot i \cdot const'_2 AZ + const'_0 \quad (30a)$$

$$E = l_2 A^2 - 6l_2 AZ + l_0 \quad (30b)$$

C. Observation of the Absolute Element l_0 of the Groups of Isotopes and correlation of l_0/l_2 with Z^2

The quotient l_0/l_2 shows a quadratic correlation with the nuclear charge number Z^2 of the type

$$l_0/l_2 = 6Z^2 + 5Z \quad (31)$$

Here, the Coulomb potential appears and increases as known by Z^2 (Figure 1E).

D. Description of the Groups of Isobars ($A=\text{constant}$)

Observation within the groups of isobars consistent of all nuclides with a constant mass number ($A = \text{constant}$) reveals a quadratic correlation between the experimental binding energies (mass defects, atomic masses as given by the KAERI) and the charge number of all nuclides in one isobaric group. This correlation is given by the formula:

$$E = const_2 \cdot Z^2 + i \cdot const_1 \cdot ZA + const_0 \quad (7a)$$

$$E = k_2 Z^2 + k_1 Z + k_0 \quad (7b)$$

(where E : binding energy; k_i : coefficient; and Z : charge number)

This square dependence reflects the Coulomb potential.

For all groups of isobars, the correlation equations were determined and the constants k_2 , k_1 , and k_0 collected. The correlation coefficients k_2 , k_1 , and k_0 were determined for all isobars and then investigated for connections and interdependencies.

E. Nuclear Radius and k_2

For all groups of isobars the constant of the quadratic portion k_2 changes with the inverse mass number $1/A^n$. This leads to a relationship of the form (E: energy, A: mass number; Z: charge number):

$$E = f_2 Z^2 / A^n + k_1 Z + k_0 \quad (32)$$

The term k_2 depends linearly on $1/A^{0.3}$ and has an inverse-linear relationship to the experimentally determined nuclear radii $k_2 = 1/r$.

F. Observation of the Ratios k_1/k_2 of the Groups of Isobars and Linear Correlation with the Mass Number A

The following discussion presents the principal findings of the calculations presented here. An extremely significant correlation was found between the k_1/k_2 ratio of the groups of isobars and the mass number A ($r^2 = 0.998$, Pearson's $r = 0.999$; Figure 2A).

Theoretically, the relative strengths of the Coulomb energy and the mass-charge binding energy would both be important. This relationship is reflected in the k_1/k_2 quotients. Correlation of these k_1/k_2 quotients with the mass number A reveals a clear interdependency of the quantities; the correlation factor is -0.8 with $r^2 = 0.998$ and Pearson's $r = 0.999$. This strongly supports a connection of the form

$$E = \text{const}_2 Z^2 + 0.8 \cdot i \cdot \text{const}_2 ZA + \text{const}_0 \quad (33a)$$

$$E = k_2 Z^2 - 0.8 \cdot k_2 ZA + k_0 \quad (33b)$$

(Figure 2A). Thus, the ZA- potential (mass-charge potential) of $-0.8 \cdot k_2 ZA$ amounts to attraction (as $0.8 \cdot i \cdot \text{const}_2 ZA$).

G. Observation of the Absolute Element k_0 of the Groups of Isobars: Quadratic Correlation of k_0/k_2 with the Mass Number A

The absolute term k_0 has a positive sign, indicating that it has a repulsive effect similar to that of the Coulomb potential. Observation of the absolute term k_0 of the isobars shows once more that there is a connection between k_0 and A. In the present case, it is a quadratic connection of the form:

$$k_0 = A^{2.7} k_2 k_2 \quad (34)$$

The question of the physical meaning of the absolute term remains open: it is either a further repulsive force, probably identical to the quark quark confinement, as postulated here, or it is an effect of the nuclear radius (i.e., an increase in nuclear radius with increasing nuclear charge number, see Figure 2E).

Therefore, $1/k_2$ represents the nuclear radius and k_1 is the mass number divided by the nuclear radius, Ak_2 . As such, the nuclear binding energy appears to be the sum of the following three parts:

(A) the Coulomb repulsion energy, $+ Z^2 / r$ (35a)

(B) the mass-charge binding energy, iZA/r or $-ZA/r$ (35b)

(C) a repulsive potential described by $+k_2 A^{2.7}$ (35c)

H. The $k_2 A^{2.7}$ Potential and the Quark Confinement

The $k_2 A^{2.7}$ potential appears as an additional repulsive potential. It appears to be almost proportional to the second or third power of the mass number and inversely proportional to the square of the radius. Thus, this potential behaves differently from all other well-known potentials. It seems to point to a repulsive strength of the form

$$m^{2.7} / r^2 \quad (36)$$

This strength seems to increase quickly with mass and to decrease quickly with increasing radius. This prompts the question, “Why does not all matter collapse?” Such a potential thus appears to be especially important on the microscale. The $k_2 A^{2.7}$ potential is best recognized as the correlation of the excess mass with the mass number, and presumably the $k_2 A^{2.7}$ potential should be identical to the quark potential (quark confinement, three color forces). The predominance of the third-power term supports this interpretation, and it probably explains the confinement, if the radius given by $A^{0.3}$ is plotted against k_0 . This figure indicates that, different from all other potentials with known $1/r$ dependence, k_0 increases with r^2 .

The quark-quark potential (quark confinement) can be both attractive and repulsive. It is attractive for an anti-symmetric interaction of quarks with different colors, particularly in the case of three-quark interactions, and it is repulsive for two quarks of the same color.

In the quark model color energy is given by exchange of a colorless gluon (colorless gluon **a** or **b**; R = red, G = green, B = blue, E = energy, \bar{R} = anti- red, \bar{G} = anti- green, \bar{B} = anti- blue):

$$\mathbf{a)} \quad 1/\sqrt{2(R\bar{R}-G\bar{G})} \qquad \mathbf{b)} \quad 1/\sqrt{6(R\bar{R}+G\bar{G}-2B\bar{B})} \quad (37a,b)$$

For two quarks of the same color:

$$E^a \propto \left(\frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}\right)^2 \geq 0 \qquad E^b \propto \left(\frac{1}{\sqrt{6}}\right)^2 \geq 0 \qquad (38a,b)$$

Taken together (combination):

$$E^\Sigma \propto \frac{2}{3} \geq 0 \Rightarrow \text{leading to repulsion} \qquad (39)$$

The exchange of two quarks with different colors (without color changing) is described by:

$$E^\Sigma \propto \left(\frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}\right) \cdot \left(-\frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}\right) + \frac{1}{\sqrt{6}} = -\frac{1}{3} \leq 0 \Rightarrow \text{leading to attraction} \qquad (40)$$

In the case where the color changes:

$$\text{Symmetric } E_{pot}^a + E_{pot}^b \propto +\frac{2}{3} \geq 0 \qquad \text{Antisymmetric } E_{pot}^a - E_{pot}^b \propto -\frac{4}{3} \leq 0 \qquad (41a,b)$$

=> repulsion

=> attraction

For three quarks:

$$E = 3 \cdot E^a - 3E^b \propto -3 \cdot \frac{4}{3} = -4 < 0 \Rightarrow \text{attraction} \qquad (42)$$

In an atomic nucleus, there are no antimatter quarks, so the repulsive potential k_0/k_2 probably results entirely or mostly from the interaction of quarks of the same color. The number of possible interactions between two quarks of the same color is given by the number of nucleon-nucleon interactions according to

$$\binom{A}{2} = \frac{A!}{(A-2)!} \qquad (43)$$

The number of three-quark interactions should be proportional to A. Interestingly; the potential k_0/k_2 shows a high correlation to

$$- \propto A!/(A-2)! \qquad (44)$$

$$- \propto A!/(A-2)! - A \qquad (45)$$

$$- \propto \binom{3A}{2} \qquad (46)$$

The correlation coefficients for these three relationships are, respectively, *Pearson's* $r = 0.992$, $r^2 = 0.98$; *Pearson's* $r = 0.992$, $r^2 = 0.98$; and *Pearson's* $r = 0.99$, $r^2 = 0.9839$.

The radius dependence of the k_0 potential shows “recurring arches”. These can be described by assuming a

$$+ \frac{4}{3} \cdot \alpha / r + k \cdot r \quad (47)$$

structure as it is typically for the quark potential.

V. DISCUSSION

A. Principal findings of the studies presented here:

1. Optimal values for both mass and charge exist in an atomic nucleus. This is seen in the parabolic nature of the nuclear binding energy plotted against either charge in the case of isobars or against mass in the case of isotopes.
2. The ratio k_1/k_2 depends on the nuclear mass number A ; since k_2 should be the inverse of the nuclear radius, this result explains the relationship between the k_1 coefficient and the mass number divided by the radius A/r .
3. Analogously, the dependency of the l_1/l_2 ratio on the charge number Z explains the relationship of the l_1 coefficient to the charge number divided by the radius Z/r .
4. Taken together, all of these dependencies can be explained by assuming that the linear term is the mass-charge product divided by the radius AZ/r .

The two treatments of isobars and isotopes presented here are mathematically equivalent to each other. The square correlation of the isobars versus the charge number includes a charge-dependent linear term whose linear correlation coefficient also depends linearly on nuclear mass. This is equivalent to the square correlation of the isotopes of an element versus the mass number since their linear terms are similarly linear mass-dependent and also linearly dependent on nuclear charge.

It appears that the new mass-charge binding energy described here could counteract the Coulomb repulsion potential. Thus, it is proposed to constitute the true nuclear binding energy. As a simple beginning, the mass-charge force of attraction can be described, analogously to the Coulomb interaction, as the product of interacting mass and charge divided by the square of the distance AZ/r^2 . As with the force equation for gravity and the Coulomb force, the mass-charge force should take the form of

$$F_{qm} = i \cdot G \cdot b \cdot \frac{m_0 Q}{r^2} \quad (48a)$$

or

$$F_{qm} = -G \cdot b \cdot \frac{m_0 Q}{r^2} \quad (48b)$$

(with $b = 11 \times 10^9 \text{ kg/C}$; G : gravitational constant; F_{qm} : charge mass force; m : mass; Q : charge; and r : radius)

The mass-charge energy is then given by

$$E_{qm} = -i \cdot G \cdot b \cdot \frac{m_0 Q}{r} \quad (49a)$$

or

$$E_{qm} = G \cdot b \cdot \frac{m_0 Q}{r} \quad (49b)$$

(where $b = 11 \times 10^9 \text{ kg/C}$ and the other variables have the same meaning as in the expression for the mass-charge force)

This raises the question, “How can mass and charge approach each other so closely within the nucleus that the resulting force of attraction outweighs the Coulomb repulsion among the positively charged protons?” In every nucleus, the mass of a nucleon is fixed at a distance r_1 from the neighboring charge, and this distance must be accounted for. The mass-charge force for each nucleon is given by the product me/r_1^2 . In summing these forces, e/r_1^2 can be factored out so that the sum of the masses then yields the theoretical nuclear mass A exactly. Analogously the Coulomb repulsion forces can be described given by Z^2/r_2^2 ; in this case, r_2 is the distance between two charges in the nucleus.

The present paper postulates that mass and charge in the atomic nucleus can approach one another so closely that the resultant force of attraction balances the Coulomb repulsion. Mass and charge must be able to simultaneously approach each other more closely than two charges. This is certainly possible e.g. with a linear arrangement of the nucleons and direct binding for two nucleons. This may also mean that the mass of a nucleon has a finite extension but that charge does not, or that the charge is mobile. These conclusions flow logically from the structure of the potential described above; moreover, they agree with quark theory. In the quark model, all very small quarks possess an electrical charge. Mass becomes substantial as a result of the quark-gluon-color interactions and, therefore, has extensions that are orders of magnitude larger than those of charges. This finite extension of mass is most likely the diameter of the nucleon ($\sim 2.4 \times 10^{-15} \text{ m}$). However, the distance between two nucleons is orders of magnitudes smaller than this. Since the extension of a neutron usually corresponds to the distance between two neighboring positive charges (protons), r_2 is given by $\sim 2.4 \times 10^{-15} \text{ m}$. Protons and neutrons approach one another at much closer distances. If the distance between two nucleons in the nucleus corresponds to a factor of $1/b$ of the extent of a

neutron, then the required conditions are fulfilled, and the distance between two nucleons corresponds to r_I .

Apparently, the nucleons within a nucleus approach one another just close enough to fulfill the equilibrium condition

$$F_c = F_{AZ} = F_{qm} \quad (50)$$

(C : Coulomb, AZ : mass-charge, F_{qm} : mass charge force). This distance is most likely predetermined from quantum mechanics or quark confinement and is fixed like an electron orbit. Similarly, the neutron appears not to be a point mass but instead to have a certain, finite extension and mass distribution. The mass-charge force described here can also be regarded as a link connecting mass-mass interactions (gravitational force) and charge-charge interactions (Coulomb force). In this way, this force may play an important role in unifying gravitation and electromagnetism.

Furthermore, the mass-charge force postulated here can provide a simple explanation for the radioactivity of unstable nuclei. Increasing the mass-charge product by increasing the positive charge in the nucleus results in beta minus decay (β^-). This process is limited by the need for neutrons to position themselves between the protons. Similarly, the Coulomb potential increases with the square of the proton number. If too few neutrons are available to separate the protons, electron capture (ec) can occur in the case that the protons approach one another too closely. In the same way, the Coulomb potential can be reduced quadratically by electron capture (ec), whereas the mass-charge potential increases linearly. Alpha decay (α) decreases the charge and mass, leading to a higher mass-charge potential. In this way, the mass-charge energy of the atomic nucleus seems to be the driving force for radioactivity.

Interestingly, charge can easily be formed from nonentity as entities of both positive and negative character. Mass, however, cannot: gravitational mass is associated with inertia, and inertia requires energy for its formation. In other words, it is as if $-i$ respectively $(-m \cdot i)$ are not connected to negative energy but instead to positive energy

$$E = |m| \cdot c^2 \quad (10)$$

“Negative energy,” therefore, does not exist.

B. Hypotheses of an Equilibrium of Forces between Coulomb Repulsion and Mass-Charge Attraction in the Atomic Nucleus

The simplest force equation for the equivalence of the Coulomb repulsion force and the mass-charge attractive force reveals proportionality between the square of the charge (Z^2) and the mass-charge product (ZA). The required linearity between the square of the charge and the mass-charge product can easily be shown. It appears that the relationship

$$Z^2 = 0.4079 \cdot AZ \quad (51)$$

is valid for all stable nuclei. This means that, in a stable nucleus, charge and mass must be in the ratio of 0.4079 to each other. Thus, the proton number should be between 0.4 and 0.6 times the neutron number, which is the case for the stable isotopes in the “valley of beta-stability”.

C. Differentiation of Energy with Respect to Charge

Taking the equation for nuclear binding energy to be

$$E = \text{const}_2 Z^2 + 0.8 \cdot i \cdot \text{const}_2 ZA \quad (52a)$$

$$E = Z^2 - 0.8 \cdot AZ \quad (52b)$$

differentiation with respect to Z yields $2Z - 0.8 \cdot A$. If there is an energy maximum, this derivative must equal zero at that point. This yields $2Z = 0.8 \cdot A$ (isotopes in the “valley of beta-stability”), which closely approaches the linearity described by $Z = 0.4079 \cdot A$. If

$$E = Z^2 - 0.8158 \cdot AZ \quad (53)$$

is used, the required linearity is achieved exactly. Similarly,

$$E = Z^2 / A^n - 0.8158 \cdot Z(A / A^n) + k_0 \quad (54)$$

can also be used.

D. Description of the Nuclear Energy as a Mass-Charge Product

The mass defect shows direct proportionality to both the nuclear mass A and the nuclear charge Z . Additionally, the binding energy E increases proportionally with respect to both the nuclear mass A and the nuclear charge Z . As a result, the binding energy can be written as the product of nuclear mass and nuclear charge, divided by the atomic radius. This mass is thought of as gravitational mass.

E. Observation of Coulomb Potential and the Mass-Charge Potential

The energy stored in the repulsion between protons in an atomic nucleus should sum to a Coulomb potential proportional to Z^2/r . Here, r is the radius of the nucleus being investigated experimentally (also see the formula of Weizsäcker). The same consideration for the mass-charge potential yields a value proportional to $-ZA/r$. In this simple formulation, the binding energy is given by the important equation

$$E = Z^2/r + i \cdot ZA/r + k_0 \quad (55a)$$

or
$$E = Z^2/r - ZA/r + k_0 \quad (55b)$$

VI. CONCLUSION

Evaluation of the results from the isobars in the isobaric equation

$$E = const_2 Z^2 + i \cdot const_1 Z + const_0 \quad (7a)$$

$$E = k_2 Z^2 + k_1 Z + k_0 \quad (7b)$$

above yields the following for the nuclear binding energy $E(Z,A)$:

$$\Delta E = k_2 Z^2 - 0.8 \cdot k_2 ZA + 0.1 \cdot k_2 A^2 - 1.6 k_2 A = k_2 Z^2 - 0.8 \cdot k_2 A(Z + 2) + 0.1 \cdot k_2 A^2 \quad (56a)$$

or

$$\Delta E = const_2 Z^2 + 0.8 \cdot i \cdot const_2 ZA + 4 \cdot 10^{-6} const_2^2 A^{2.7} \quad (56b)$$

$$\Delta E = k_2 Z^2 - 0.8 \cdot k_2 ZA + 4 \cdot 10^{-6} k_2 k_2 A^{2.7} \quad (56c)$$

The analogous procedure regarding the isotope observations

($E = const'_2 \cdot A^2 + i \cdot const'_1 \cdot ZA + const'_0$; or $E = l_2 A^2 + l_1 A + l_0$) yields:

$$\Delta E = const'_2 A^2 + 6 \cdot i \cdot const'_2 ZA + 6.6 \cdot const'_2 Z^2 - 66 \cdot const'_2 Z \quad (57a)$$

$$\Delta E = l_2 A^2 - 6 \cdot l_2 ZA + 6.6 \cdot l_2 Z^2 - 66 \cdot l_2 Z \quad (57b)$$

Taking the quark-quark potential into account yields:

$$\Delta E = const_2 Z^2 + 0.8 \cdot i \cdot const_2 ZA + 0.095 \cdot (k_2 A! / (A - 2)! - A) \quad (58a)$$

$$\Delta E = k_2 Z^2 - 0.8 \cdot k_2 ZA + 0.095 \cdot (k_2 A! / (A - 2)! - A) \quad (58b)$$

These equations consist the terms $-0.8k_2ZA$ and/or $-6l_2ZA$ corresponding to the term $i \cdot const_2 ZA$ which we have proposed in equation (7) at the beginning. This term is regarded to describe the charge mass binding energy related to the imaginary part $i \cdot Z/A$ deriving from the

interaction of the nucleons among themselves $(bZ,A) \times (bZ,A) = (bZ,A)^2$. Thereby, the last proposed formula for the nuclear binding energy (mass defect) is completely consistent with the Bethe-Weizsäcker formula. It is possible to transform the Bethe-Weizsäcker formula into a quadratic: $E = const_2 Z^2 + i \cdot const_1 Z + const_0$ or $E = k_2 Z^2 + k_1 Z + k_0$. In this case, k_1 is not a function of the mass number A but is a constant, and k_1 results from the “asymmetric term”. The calculations described here show that the experimental data (atomic masses, Figure 2C) require a linear term of the form $-0.8k_2 AZ$. It is also possible to retain all the terms of the Bethe-Weizsäcker formula with the exception of the asymmetric term, which should be replaced by $-0.8k_2 AZ$. From this perspective, the formulas given here would improve those derived by Bethe and Weizsäcker.

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Figure Legends

FIG. 1.

Figures 1-5 show the dependencies of the square correlation coefficients (l_2, l_1, l_0) of the nuclear binding energy (KAERI, G Audi, and AH Wapstra) and the mass number A ($E = const'_2 \cdot A^2 + i \cdot const'_1 \cdot ZA + const'_0$; or $E = l_2 A^2 + l_1 A + l_0$) for all known *isotopes of each element* (groups of isotopes, $N = 3000$ nuclides).

FIG. 1(a).

The correlation of l_1/l_2 as a function of the charge number Z . A relationship of the form $l_1/l_2 = -6Z$ can be recognized. The product $-6 l_2 Z A$ describes the second, linear term. This result confirms the existence of the mass-charge energy, since it shows that the linear, mass-dependent term depends linearly on charge.

FIG. 1(b).

The variation in the coefficient l_2 as a function of the charge number Z for all different *isotopes of all elements (groups of isotopes)*. Thus, l_2 is interpreted as the reciprocal value of the radius ($1/r$). It is clear that l_2 is connected with $1/Z$. In other words, the radius increases with increasing nuclear charge number and, thus, increasing mass number ($r \sim Z \sim A$).

FIG. 1(c).

The variation of the coefficient l_1 with the charge number Z for all different *isotopes of all elements (groups of isotopes)*. l_1 is interpreted as the ratio of charge to radius (*charge density*).

FIG. 1(d).

The variation of the coefficient l_0 with the charge number Z for all different *isotopes of all elements (groups of isotopes)*.

FIG. 1(e).

The variation of the quotient l_0/l_2 with the charge number Z . A square function of the form $l_0/l_2 = -6.6Z^2 - 66Z$ can be recognized. This corresponds to the repulsive Coulombic potential.

FIG. 2.

The dependencies of the correlation coefficients (k_2, k_1, k_0) of the nuclear binding energy (KAERI, G Audi, and AH Wapstra) on the charge Z ($E = const_2 \cdot Z^2 + i \cdot const_1 \cdot ZA + const_0$ or $E = k_2 Z^2 + k_1 Z + k_0$) for all known *groups of isobars* ($N = 3000$ nuclides).

FIG. 2(a).

The correlation between k_1/k_2 and the mass number A .

A relationship of the form $k_1 / k_2 = -0.8A$ can be recognized. The product $-0.8 k_2 A Z$ describes the second, linear term. As in the case of isotopes, this result appears to confirm the existence of the mass-charge energy. It clearly shows that the linear charge-dependent term $k_1 Z$ depends linearly on mass.

FIG. 2(b).

The variation of the coefficient k_2 with the mass number A for all different *groups of isobars*. The coefficient k_2 is related to the inverse nuclear radius ($1/r$). The map shows that the nuclear radius increases with the number of nucleons A .

FIG. 2(c).

The variation of the coefficient k_1 with the mass number A for all different *groups of isobars*. k_1 is interpreted as the ratio of mass to radius.

FIG. 2(d).

The variation of the coefficient k_0 with the mass number A for all different *groups of isobars*. The term k_0 is thus interpreted as a repulsive quark-quark potential. It increases rapidly with the number of nucleons due to the increasing number of possible interactions.

FIG. 2(e).

The variation of the quotient k_0/k_2 with the charge number Z . A square function of the form $k_0 / k_2 = 0.1A^2 - A$ can be recognized. The square increase with the nucleon number is due to the increase in the number of possible quark-quark interactions.

Figure 1
ISOTOPS Z=konst

Figure 2
ISOBARS A=const

